

Supplementary Material for the paper:
Investigating the role of dispersion corrections and anharmonic effects on the phase transition of SrZrS₃: A systematic analysis from AIMD free energy calculations

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SI. EFFECTS OF DISPERSION CORRECTIONS ON LATTICE GEOMETRY AND ENERGIES OF NL AND DP PHASES AT 0K

The lattice geometries and energies of SrZrS₃ in NL and DP phases relaxed using uncorrected PBE [S1], and PBE with D2 [S2] D3(0) and D3(BJ) [S3], TS [S4], TS/HI [S5, S6], MBD/FI [S7, S8], and dDsC [S9] dispersion correction methods are shown in Tab. S1.

TABLE S1: Lattice parameters (a , b and c), cell volume (V) and energies per formula unit determined for the NL and DP phases via structural relaxations using different dispersion schemes. The values of structural parameters are compared against experiments extrapolated at 0 K [S10].

Method	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V (Å ³ /f.u.)	E (eV/f.u.)
NL phase					
Exp. (298 K)	8.525	3.826	13.925	113.5	
Exp. (0 K)	8.509	3.806	13.834	112.0	
PBE	8.648	3.840	14.015	116.3	-31.553
PBE+D2	8.444	3.802	14.037	112.7	-32.842
PBE+D3(0)	8.566	3.809	13.897	113.4	-32.672
PBE+D3(BJ)	8.427	3.797	13.844	110.7	-33.352
PBE+TS	8.367	3.806	13.979	111.3	-33.717
PBE+TS/HI	8.499	3.791	13.851	111.6	-32.636
PBE+MBD/FI	8.289	3.739	13.660	105.8	-34.060
PBE+dDsC	8.504	3.810	13.904	112.6	-32.508
DP phase					
Exp. (298 K)	7.108	9.772	6.741	117.1	
Exp. (0 K)	7.098	9.731	6.704	115.8	
PBE	7.169	9.829	6.787	119.6	-31.551
PBE+D2	7.126	9.798	6.690	116.8	-32.743
PBE+D3(0)	7.121	9.762	6.746	117.2	-32.675
PBE+D3(BJ)	7.106	9.728	6.677	115.4	-33.276
PBE+TS	7.012	9.699	6.830	116.1	-33.838
PBE+TS/HI	7.096	9.759	6.722	116.4	-32.543
PBE+MBD/FI	7.112	9.597	6.413	109.4	-34.026
PBE+dDsC	7.129	9.767	6.715	116.9	-32.426

SII. COMPARING FREE ENERGIES OBTAINED USING SEMI-CLASSICAL AND QUANTUM THEORIES

Quantum mechanical (QM) analogue of eq. 2 (presented in the main text) for semi-classical (SC) free energy within the HA approach writes:

$$A(T) = A_{el}(\mathbf{s}_{V_0(T=0K)}, \mathbf{h}_{V_0(T=0K)}) + k_B T \sum_{p=1}^{3N-3} \ln \left[1 - \exp \left(\frac{-\hbar\omega_p(\mathbf{s}_{V_0(T=0K)}, \mathbf{h}_{V_0(T=0K)})}{k_B T} \right) \right], \quad (\text{S1})$$

and similar QM analogues can be defined in a straightforward manner also for eq. 3 (S-QHA approach) and 4 (AIMD-QHA approach). In Tab. S2, numerical results of SC and QM Gibbs free energies and transition temperatures obtained using HA, S-QHA, AIMD-QHA and TI approaches are compared. Although the SC and QM expressions lead different values of free energies computed for the given structure and set of thermodynamic conditions, the differences in $\Delta G_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ are only small leading to differences in predicted $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ within 5 K. Hence, for the sake of consistency with our AIMD calculations that generate semi-classical ensembles, we chose to use SC method in all calculations presented in the main text.

TABLE S2: Dependence of the Gibbs free energy of SrZrS₃ in the NL and DP phase on T computed using semiclassical and quantum mechanical (values in parentheses) expressions. The values obtained from harmonic approximation (G_{HA}), static-QHA (G_{S-QHA}), AIMD-QHA ($G_{AIMD-QHA}$), and TI (G_{TI}) are compared. The term $\Delta G_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ represents the free energy difference between NL and DP phase and $T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$ is the corresponding transition temperature.

T (K)	G_{HA} (eV/f.u.)	G_{S-QHA} (eV/f.u.)	$G_{AIMD-QHA}$ (eV/f.u.)	G_{TI} (eV/f.u.)
NL phase				
0	-32.6367 (-32.4608)	-32.6367 (-32.4615)	-32.6367 (-32.4615)	-32.6367 (-32.4615)
300	-32.7178 (-32.7019)	-32.7220 (-32.7066)	-32.7216 (-32.7062)	-32.7236 (-32.7082)
600	-33.3331 (-33.3250)	-33.3507 (-33.3432)	-33.3502 (-33.3427)	-33.3544 (-33.3469)
900	-34.1500 (-34.1446)	-34.1914 (-34.1866)	-34.1910 (-34.1862)	-34.1983 (-34.1934)
DP phase				
0	-32.5438 (-32.3779)	-32.5438 (-32.3788)	-32.5438 (-32.3788)	-32.5438 (-32.3788)
300	-32.6588 (-32.6439)	-32.6632 (-32.6490)	-32.6631 (-32.6487)	-32.6639 (-32.6495)
600	-33.3079 (-33.3004)	-33.3245 (-33.3176)	-33.3250 (-33.3180)	-33.3273 (-33.3203)
900	-34.1587 (-34.1537)	-34.1965 (-34.1921)	-34.1992 (-34.1947)	-34.2016 (-34.1971)
$\Delta G_{NL \rightarrow DP}$				
0	0.0930 (0.0929)	0.0929 (0.0826)	0.0929 (0.0826)	0.0929 (0.0826)
300	0.0591 (0.0580)	0.0588 (0.0577)	0.0586 (0.0575)	0.0597 (0.0586)
600	0.0253 (0.0246)	0.0262 (0.0256)	0.0252 (0.0247)	0.0271 (0.0266)
900	-0.0086 (-0.0091)	-0.0051 (-0.0055)	-0.0082 (-0.0085)	-0.0033 (-0.0037)
$T_{NL \rightarrow DP}$				
	824 K (819 K)	851 K (847 K)	826 K (823 K)	867 K (864 K)

SIII. COMPARING THE THERMAL EFFECTS ON STRUCTURES OF NL AND DP PHASES FOR DIFFERENT PBE FUNCTIONALS

In this section, we compare the performance of different dispersion correction methods for finite- T structural predictions in both the phases. A detailed analysis of thermal effects on the DP phase using the PBE and PBE+D3(0) functionals has already been reported in our previous work. [S11, S12] Lattice parameters along with volume per formula unit of NL and DP phases obtained from NPT AIMD simulations performed at all three levels (PBE, PBE+D3(0) and PBE+TS/HI) are presented for the T range 0 to 1200 K (the result of 0 K corresponds to the result of static relaxation) in Table S3 and S4. The lattice parameters are shifted to lower values upon employing the PBE+D3(0) functional as compared to the uncorrected PBE values, as previously reported. [S12] The values are further reduced when the TS/HI correction is used. As is evident from Fig. S1, the differences between the a , b and c lattice parameters obtained from PBE+D3(0) and PBE+TS/HI methods are quite modest in the NL phase, extremely negligible for the b and c parameters of the DP phase but quite significant for the a parameter of the DP phase.

TABLE S3: Lattice constants (a , b and c) and cell volume (V_1) per formula unit obtained for NL phase of SrZrS₃ in temperature range 0-1200 K using PBE, PBE+D3(0) [S11, S12] and PBE+TS/HI methods.

T (K)	Type	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V_1 (Å ³ /f.u.)
NL phase					
0	PBE	8.649	3.840	14.015	116.3
	PBE+D3(0)	8.566	3.809	13.897	113.4
	PBE+TS/HI	8.499	3.791	13.851	111.6
300	PBE	8.674	3.858	14.098	117.9
	PBE+D3(0)	8.582	3.829	13.988	114.9
	PBE+TS/HI	8.525	3.810	13.943	113.2
	exp [S10]	8.525	3.826	13.925	113.5
	exp [S13]	8.504	3.820	13.917	113.0
600	PBE	8.713	3.878	14.185	119.8
	PBE+D3	8.611	3.849	14.076	116.6
	PBE+TS/HI	8.559	3.831	14.031	115.0
900	PBE	8.758	3.901	14.277	121.9
	PBE+D3(0)	8.643	3.870	14.162	118.4
	PBE+TS/HI	8.599	3.852	14.116	116.8
1200	PBE	8.815	3.926	14.372	124.3
	PBE+D3(0)	8.679	3.893	14.254	120.3
	PBE+TS/HI	8.637	3.875	14.206	118.8

It can be observed that the thermal trend of each lattice constant obtained from the three methods are almost the same. Thus, the choice of dispersion correction scheme does not alter the course of thermally driven structural changes; however, the values obtained from the PBE+TS/HI method are closer to experimental results. It has been previously demonstrated that a phase transition from DP to undistorted cubic phase occurs quasi-continuously upon heating [S11, S12], and this has been confirmed using all three approaches. In particular, the RDF_{Zr-S} obtained from the calculations at different levels of theory are nearly identical (see Fig. S2), suggesting that the D3(0) and TS/HI dispersion corrections of PBE have only a minor influence on the internal structure of SrZrS₃. This minor influence on the interatomic distances that are beyond nearest neighbors results from the overall decrease in the lattice parameters that was previously discussed. In summary, the PBE + TS/HI functional is successful in accurately depicting the thermal changes in structure and the well-known DP to C phase transition at elevated temperatures.

TABLE S4: Lattice constants (a , b and c) and cell volume (V_1) per formula unit obtained for DP phase of SrZrS₃ in temperature range 0-1200 K using PBE, PBE+D3(0) [S11, S12] and PBE+TS/HI methods.

T (K)	Type	a (Å)	b (Å)	c (Å)	V_1 (Å ³ /f.u.)
DP phase					
0	PBE	7.169	9.829	6.787	119.5
	PBE+D3(0)	7.121	9.761	6.746	117.2
	PBE+TS/HI	7.096	9.759	6.722	116.4
300	PBE	7.177	9.868	6.827	120.9
	PBE+D3(0)	7.131	9.802	6.783	118.5
	PBE+TS/HI	7.098	9.800	6.772	117.7
	exp [S10]	7.108	9.772	6.741	117.0
	exp [S13]	7.103	9.758	6.731	116.6
600	PBE	7.182	9.915	6.876	112.4
	PBE+D3(0)	7.138	9.846	6.827	119.9
	PBE+TS/HI	7.098	9.845	6.824	119.2
900	PBE	7.182	9.973	6.936	124.2
	PBE+D3(0)	7.139	9.899	6.879	121.5
	PBE+TS/HI	7.092	9.897	6.882	120.7
1200	PBE	7.150	10.037	7.033	126.1
	PBE+D3(0)	7.133	9.956	6.942	123.2
	PBE+TS/HI	7.084	9.956	6.954	122.6
1200 (c)	PBE	7.099	10.031	7.098	126.3
	PBE+D3(0)	7.041	9.952	7.041	123.3
	PBE+TS/HI	7.032	9.926	7.032	122.6

Figure S1: Comparison of the thermal variation of scaled lattice parameters for the NL ($a' = a/2$, $b' = b$, $c' = c/4$) and DP ($a' = a/\sqrt{2}$, $b' = b/2$, $c' = c/\sqrt{2}$) phases of SrZrS₃ obtained using PBE (dotted lines), PBE+D3(0) (dashed lines) and PBE+TS/HI (solid lines) functionals. Note the black, red and green color represent a' , b' and c' lattice parameters, respectively. Similar thermal trends is observed in results of PBE+D3 and PBE+TS/HI methods, showing a significant improvement over uncorrected PBE.

Figure S2: Radial distribution function ($\text{RDF}_{\text{Zr-S}}$) of Zr-S distances in the DP phase of SrZrS_3 obtained using PBE, PBE+D3(0) and PBE+TS/HI functional at a) 300 K and b) 1200 K respectively.

SIV. QUALITY OF THE MLFF

Tab. S5 shows error metrics determined for the machine-learned force-fields (MLFF) used in calculations of NL and DP phases of SrZrS₃ at different temperatures. For each T and phase, the metrics were evaluated using test set of 250 configurations randomly chosen from the corresponding NVT MD production run for $\lambda = 1$. The effect of imperfect MLFF on computed free energies was reduced via free energy perturbation theory [S14], as described in section III.B.3 of the main text. The corresponding correction terms $A_{1,DFT} - A_{1,MLFF}$ are also listed in Tab. S5.

TABLE S5: Potential energy difference calculated from DFT and MLFF were compared and the corresponding mean error (ME), mean absolute error (MEA) and root mean square error (RMSE) are presented in this table. Free energy difference ($A_{1,DFT} - A_{1,MLFF}$) computed using perturbation theory (see eq. 8 in the main text) are also listed.

T (K)	ME (meV/f.u.)	MAE (meV/f.u.)	RMSE (meV/f.u.)	$A_{1,DFT} - A_{1,MLFF}$ (meV/f.u.)
NL phase				
300	0.4	1.0	1.2	-0.14
600	0.1	2.0	2.5	-1.8 (0.036)
900	2.4	4.1	5.0	-1.7
DP phase				
300	1.0	1.5	1.8	-0.3
600	1.7	3.1	3.8	-1.8
900	5.4	5.9	7.2	0.7

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